

DOI: 10.15276/ETR.02.2023.7

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8155029

UDC: 331.3

JEL: J22, J24

THE EFFECT OF COMMUNICATION AND WORK ENVIRONMENT ON PERFORMANCE WITH MOTIVATION AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE IN THE SECRETARIAT DPRD LABUHAN BATU

ВПЛИВ КОМУНІКАЦІЇ ТА РОБОЧОГО СЕРЕДОВИЩА НА ПРОДУКТИВНІСТЬ З МОТИВАЦІЄЮ ЯК ПРОМІЖНОЮ ЗМІННОЮ В СЕКРЕТАРІАТІ DPRD ЛАБУХАН БАТУ

Syafrizal Zan

Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia

ORCID: 0000-0001-8447-821X

Yusuf Ronny Edward

Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia

ORCID: 0000-0001-8769-5164

Lenta Friska Purba

Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia

ORCID: 0000-0002-9679-1789

Faisal Akbar

Universitas Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia

ORCID: 0000-0003-3710-149X

Received 22.02.2023

Syafrizal Zan, Yusuf Ronny Edward, Lenta Friska Purba, Faisal Akbar. Вплив комунікації та робочого середовища на продуктивність з мотивацією як проміжною змінною в Секретаріаті DPRD Лабухан Бату. Оглядова стаття.

Людські ресурси є головним фактором розвитку ділового світу. Людські ресурси в організації – це всі люди, які беруть участь у розвитку компанії, особливо співробітники. Для досягнення організаційних цілей організації потрібен компетентний і креативний співробітник. Співробітники відіграють важливу роль в організації, а саме як мислителі, планувальники та контролери організаційної діяльності. Дослідження проводилося на 53 співробітниках із застосуванням методу насиченої вибірки. Використана техніка збору даних: первинні дані у формі анкет та вторинні дані, отримані шляхом вивчення документації. Техніка аналізу даних використовувала кількісні дані, які були оброблені за допомогою програми SPSS версії 25, а саме t-тест, тест Собея та аналіз шляхів.

Ключові слова: спілкування, робоче середовище, мотивація, продуктивність

Syafrizal Zan, Yusuf Ronny Edward, Lenta Friska Purba, Faisal Akbar The Effect of Communication and Work Environment on Performance With Motivation as an Intervening Variable in the Secretariat DPRD Labuhan Batu. Review article.

Human resources are the main factor in the development of the business world. Human resources in the organization are all people involved in developing the company, especially employees. An organization needs a competent and creative employee to achieve organizational goals. Employees have an important role in an organization, namely as thinkers, planners and controllers of organizational activities. The study was conducted on 53 employees using a saturated sampling technique. The data collection technique used was primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique used quantitative data which was processed using the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis.

Keywords: communication, work environment, motivation, performance

Human resources are the main factor in the development of the business world. Human resources in the organization are all people involved in developing the company, especially employees. An organization needs a competent and creative employee to achieve organizational goals. Employees have an important role in an organization, namely as thinkers, planners and controllers of organizational activities. Seeing the importance of the role of employees in the organization, employee performance determines the success or achievement of the company.

Employee performance is the result of work achieved by a person or group of people or a group of people in an organization, according to their respective authorities and responsibilities in order to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, not violating the law and in accordance with morals and ethics, (Sutrisno, 2010).

Performance basically focuses on problems in the process of planning, implementation, and also the results obtained after carrying out the work. Performance is usually referred to as an answer to the success or failure of the initial goals of the work program and policies that have been set. Matters regarding performance are very important, because performance is one of the most important measures of organizational quality.

An employee is said to have good performance if the employee is able to produce results that equal or exceed the standards or criteria that have been set together in the organization. Conversely, employees are said to have no performance if the work results are less than the standards or criteria that have been set together.

The Main Duties of the Secretariat of the DPRD Labuhanbatu Regency carry out secretarial and financial administration, support carrying out the duties and functions of the DPRD, as well as providing and coordinating the experts needed by the DPRD in providing their rights and functions as needed. The progress of the Labuhanbatu Regency DPRD Secretariat is greatly influenced by the performance of its employees. Good performance is influenced by a good level of ability as well. However, based on the results of the initial research obtained by researchers, there is a phenomenon of decreased employee performance that can affect organizational performance. This is caused by decreased employee motivation at work. With this, the organization needs to pay attention to and meet the needs of employees in carrying out work so that the organization can overcome and improve problems that occur within the organization by providing motivation to employees to foster morale within the employee.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Performance. Performance is a real behavior that is displayed by everyone as work performance produced by employees according to their role in the agency. Performance is a very important thing in an agency's efforts to achieve its goals.

According to Donni (2018: 269) Performance is the level of success of employees in completing their work. Meanwhile, according to Robbin in Kasmir (2018: 183) Performance is a function of ability, motivation, and opportunity.

According to Irianto in Sutrisno (2010: 171) Performance is an achievement obtained by someone in carrying out a task. And the success of the organization depends on the performance of the relevant organizational actors. Mangkunegara in the Mariani Journal et al (2017) Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties according to the responsibilities given to him.

Based on the definition above, it can be concluded that performance is a process of carrying out an activity that is given to employees according to their work and ability to achieve maximum work results and achievements in the organization.

The main part

Motivation. Motivation comes from the Latin word *movere* which means encouragement or driving force from within humans to act or behave. Motivation is the driving force that causes a person to be willing and willing to mobilize abilities in the form of expertise or skills, energy and time to carry out various activities. The definition of motivation is also inseparable from the word need or "need" or "want".

Need is a potential in humans that needs to be responded to or responded to.

According to Hamali (2012: 131) Motivation is an innate desire caused by needs, desires, and wills that encourage an individual to use his physical and mental energy to achieve the desired goals.

Meanwhile, according to Stefan Ivanko (2012: 131) Motivation is a person's desire and energy directed to achieving a goal. Efforts to influence someone in order to provide motivation means getting then wanting to do something that is known and should be done.

According to Siagian in Agustini (2011: 32), what is meant by employee motivation is the driving force that results in a member of the organization willing and willing to direct abilities in the form of expertise and skills of personnel and time to carry out various activities that are their responsibility and fulfill their obligations, in order to achieve the objectives and various targets that have been determined by the previous agency.

This is in accordance with what Abraham described in Mangkunegara (2013: 93) motivation is a tendency to be active, starting from the drive and ending with self-adjustment. Adjustment is said to satisfy motivation.

Communication. According to Hamali (2018: 224) Communication is a process of conveying ideas and information in the form of orders and work instructions from a leader to employees or subordinates to carry out work tasks as well as possible.

According to Handoko (2012: 272) communication is the process of transferring meaning in the form of ideas or information from one person to another. The purpose of the communication process is to achieve mutual understanding between the two parties. Before messages are sent to the communicant, the communicator gives the meanings in the message (decode) which are then captured by the communicant and given meaning according to the concept they have (encode).

Working environment. Working environment conditions greatly affect employee job satisfaction. The work environment is an environment where employees work and can influence them in carrying out the assigned tasks. Some experts define the work environment as follows:

Sedarmayati (2013:1) states that the work environment is all the tools and materials encountered, the surrounding environment in which a person works, his work methods, and work arrangements both as individuals and as a group.

According to Nitisemito (2010: 183) defines the work environment as everything that is around workers who can influence themselves in carrying out the tasks assigned.

Meanwhile, according to Scultz and Schultz in Mangkunegara (2017: 105) argued that the environment or working conditions are all the physical aspects of psychological work and work regulations that can affect job satisfaction and achievement of work productivity (figure 1).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework, hypothesis development
Source: authors' own elaboration

A hypothesis is a temporary answer to a research problem, until proven through the data collected. The hypothesis of this research is:

- H1: Communication has a significant effect on motivation.
- H2: The work environment has a significant effect on motivation.
- H3: Communication has a significant effect on performance.

H4: The work environment has a significant effect on performance.

H5: Motivation has a significant effect on performance.

H6: Communication has a significant effect on performance through motivation.

H7: The work environment has a significant effect on performance through motivation

RESULT. SUB MODEL T TEST RESULTS.

Table 1. Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	48.831	7.006		6.970	0.000
	Communication	0.215	0.129	0.229	1.661	0.003
	Working Enviroment	0.227	0.110	0.233	1.243	0.009

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation
Source: authors' own elaboration

In the table, the t statistical test is obtained as follows:

1. Communication Variable (X_1) with a probability level of 0.003. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0.003 < \alpha = 0.05$, accept the hypothesis that communication has a significant effect on motivational variables.

2. Work Environment Variable (X_2) with a probability level of 0.009. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0.009 < \alpha = 0.05$, so accept the hypothesis that the work environment variable has a significant effect on motivational variables.

Thus the path analysis equation can be arranged as follows:

$$Z = 0.229 X_1 + 0.233 X_2$$

The analysis equation model means:

1. Communication Variable (X_1) = 0.229
Communication variables that are positive means that they have a unidirectional influence, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the communication variable will increase the value of the motivational variable by 0.229 per one unit score.

2. Work Environment Variable (X_2) = 0.233. A work environment variable that has a positive sign means that it has a unidirectional effect, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score for the work environment variable will increase the value of the motivational variable by 0.233 per one unit score.

Figure 2. Path Analysis
Source: authors' own elaboration

Path Analysis of Sub Model I.

1) Referring to the regression output of Sub Model I, it can be seen that the significance value of the two variables is Communication (X_1) = 0.003 and Work Environment (X_2) = 0.009. These results conclude

that the regression of Sub Model I, namely the Communication variable (X_1) has a significant effect on Motivation (Z), and the Work Environment variable (X_2) has a significant effect on Motivation (Z). The value of R2 or R Square.

Table 2. Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	46.163	10.132		4.556	0.000
	Communication	0.031	0.137	0.033	4.225	0.023
	Working Enviroment	0.045	0.113	0.057	4.400	0.001
	Motivation	0.018	0.146	0.118	4.121	0.005

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

Source: authors' own elaboration

Sub Model II Test Results.

Primary Data Processed, 2023.

In the table, the t statistical test is obtained, as follows:

1. Motivation variable (Z), with a probability level of 0.005. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0.005 < \hat{\alpha} = 0.05$, so accept the hypothesis that motivation variables have a significant effect on performance.

2. Communication Variable (X_1), with a probability level of 0.023. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0.023 < \hat{\alpha} = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that the communication variable has a significant effect on performance.

3. Work Environment Variable (X_2), with a probability level of 0.001. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0.001 < \hat{\alpha} = 0.05$, so accept the hypothesis that work environment variables have a significant effect on performance.

Thus the path analysis equation can be arranged as follows:

$$Y = 0.033 X_1 + 0.057 X_2 + 0.118 Z.$$

The analysis equation model means:

1. Communication Variable (X_1) = 0.033. A communication variable with a positive sign means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one communication variable score unit will increase the performance variable value by 0.033 per one score unit.

2. Work Environment Variable (X_2) = 0.057. Work environment variables that have a positive sign mean that they have a unidirectional effect, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score for the work environment variable will increase the value of the performance variable by 0.057 per one score unit.

3. Motivational Variable (Z) = 0.118. A motivational variable that has a positive sign means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the motivational variable will increase the

value of the performance variable by 0.188 per one unit score.

Sobel test.

Testing the mediation hypothesis can also be carried out with a procedure developed by Sobel and known as the Sobel test (Sobel test). The Sobel test is carried out by testing the strength of the indirect influence X to Y through Z, as follows:

$$Z = \frac{ab}{\sqrt{b^2SE_a^2 + a^2SE_b^2}}, \quad (1)$$

where A = regression coefficient of the independent variable on the mediating variable

B – regression coefficient of the mediating variable on the dependent variable

Se_a – standard error of estimation from the influence of the independent variable on the mediating variable

Se_b – standard error of estimation of the effect of the mediating variable on the dependent variable

The following are the results of the Sobel test with communication variables on performance through motivation.

$$t = \frac{0.229 \times 0.118}{\sqrt{(0.118^2 \times 0.129^2) + (0.229^2 \times 0.146^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.229 \times 0.118}{\sqrt{0.0002317093 + 0.0011178324}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.027022}{0.0013495417}$$

$$t = 20.023.$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above, a t value of 20,023 is obtained, so that a t count value of 20,023 > t table 4,447 is obtained. It can be concluded that the motivational variable is able to mediate the relationship between the influence of communication on performance.

The following are the results of the Sobel test with work environment variables on performance through motivation.

$$t = \frac{0.223 \times 0.118}{\sqrt{(0.118^2 \times 0.110^2) + (0.233^2 \times 0.146^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.233 \times 0.118}{\sqrt{0.0001684804 + 0.0011572243}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.027494}{0.0013257047}$$

$$t = 20.739.$$

Path Analysis Sub Model II.

Referring to the output of the Model II regression in the table section, it can be seen that the significance

values of the three variables are: Communication (X_1) = 0.023, Work Environment (X_2) = 0.001, Motivation (Z) = 0.005. These results conclude that the regression of Sub Model II, namely the variables Communication (X_1) and Motivation (Z) have no significant effect on performance (Y). But the Work Environment variable (X_2) has a significant effect on performance (Y). The value of R^2 or R Square contained in the Model Summary table is 0.232, this shows that the contribution or contribution to the influence of Communication (X_1), Work Environment (X_2) and Motivation (Z) on Performance (Y) is 58%, while the rest 42% is the contribution of other variables not included in the study. Meanwhile, the value of e^2 can be found using the formula $e^2 = \tilde{\alpha} (1 - 0.232) = 0.876$. Thus the path diagram of the structure model II is obtained as follows (figure 3).

Figure 3. Path Analysis
Source: authors' own elaboration

The results of the analysis show that the direct influence given by Communication (X_1) on Performance (Y) is 0.033. Meanwhile, the indirect effect of communication (X_1) on performance (Y) through motivation (Z), is $0.229 \times 0.057 = 0.013$. Then the total effect given by the Communication variable (X_1) on Performance (Y) is the direct effect plus the indirect effect, namely $0.033 + 0.013 = 0.046$. Based on the calculation results above, it can be seen that the direct effect value is 0.033 and the indirect effect is 0.046, which means that the direct effect value is greater than the indirect effect value. These results indicate that indirectly the variable Communication (X_1) through Motivation (Z) has no significant effect on performance (Y).

The results of the analysis show that the direct influence of the work environment (X_2) on performance (Y) is 0.233. Meanwhile, the indirect effect of the work environment (X_2) on performance (Y) through motivation (Z), is $0.233 \times 0.118 = 0.027$. Then the total effect given by the Work Environment variable (X_2) on Performance (Y) is the direct effect plus the indirect effect, namely $0.057 + 0.027 = 0.084$. Based on the calculation results above, it can be seen that the direct effect value is 0.057 and the indirect effect is 0.084, which means that the direct effect value is greater than the indirect effect value. These results indicate that indirectly the work environment variable (X_2) through motivation (Z) has no significant effect on performance (Y).

DISCUSSION. Effect of Communication on Motivation.

The communication variable has a positive and significant effect on motivation at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. The communication variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.229 and has a unidirectional effect, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the communication variable will increase the motivational value of the employees of the DPRD Secretariat Kab. Labuhanbatu of 0.229 per one unit score.

Effect of Work Environment on Motivation.

The work environment variable has a positive and significant effect on motivation at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. The work environment variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.233 and has a unidirectional effect, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score for the work environment variable will increase the motivational value of the employees of the DPRD Secretariat Kab. Labuhanbatu 0.233 per one score unit.

Effect of Communication on Performance.

The communication variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. The communication variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.033 and has a unidirectional effect, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score for the communication variable will increase the

performance value of the employees of the DPRD Secretariat Kab. Labuhanbatu of 0.033 per one unit score.

Effect of Work Environment on Performance.

The work environment variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. The work environment variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.057 and has a unidirectional effect, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score for the work environment variable will add to the performance value of the Kab. DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu of 0.057 per one unit score.

Effect of Motivation on Performance.

The motivational variable has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. The motivational variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.118 and has a unidirectional effect, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the motivational variable will increase the performance value of the employees of the DPRD Secretariat Kab. Labuhanbatu of 0.118 per one unit score.

Effect of Communication on Performance through Motivation.

Based on the results of the sobel test calculations, it is known that the t value is 20.023, so that the t count value is $20.023 > t$ table 4.447. It can be concluded that the motivational variable is able to mediate the relationship between the influence of communication on performance. And based on path analysis, it is known that the influence of communication (X_1) on the performance (Y) of the employees of the DPRD Secretariat Kab. Labuhanbatu is 4.6%, which consists of a direct effect of 11.8% and an indirect effect of communication (X_1) on performance (Y) through motivation (Z) of 1.3%. The results of this calculation indicate that the direct effect of communication (X_1) on performance (Y) is greater than the indirect effect. Thus it can be said that communication is effective in improving performance, in other words it can be emphasized that communication (X_1) has an influence if there is an increase in employee performance in carrying out tasks.

The Effect of the Work Environment on Performance through Competence.

Based on the results of the sobel test calculation, it is known that the t value is 20.739, so that the t value is $20.739 > t$ table 4.447. It can be concluded that the motivation variable is able to mediate the relationship between the influence of the work environment on performance. And based on path analysis, it is known that the influence of the work environment (X_2) on

the performance (Y) of the employees of the DPRD Secretariat of Kab. Labuhanbatu is 8.4%, which consists of a direct effect of 5.7% and an indirect effect of the work environment (X_2) on performance (Y) through motivation (Z) of 2.7%. The results of this calculation indicate that the direct effect of the work environment (X_2) on performance (Y) is greater than the indirect effect. Thus it can be said that the influence of the work environment (X_2) will be smaller in increasing performance (Y) if it is done through motivation (Z).

Conclusions

1. Communication has a positive and significant effect on motivation at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that communication can increase employee motivation.

2. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on motivation at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that the work environment can increase employee motivation.

3. Communication has a positive and significant effect on performance at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that communication can improve performance.

4. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on performance at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that the work environment can improve employee performance.

5. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance at the District DPRD Secretariat. Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that the higher the motivation of employees can improve performance.

6. The influence of communication on the performance of employees of the DPRD Secretariat Kab. Labuhanbatu will be smaller if done through motivation. The direct effect of communication on employee performance is greater than the indirect effect of communication on performance. It can be concluded that motivation is not able to mediate the influence of communication on performance.

7. The influence of the work environment on the performance of employees of the DPRD Secretariat Kab. Labuhanbatu will be smaller if done through motivation. The direct effect of the work environment on performance is greater than the indirect effect of the work environment on performance. It can be concluded that motivation is not able to mediate the influence of the work environment on performance.

Abstract

Human resources are the main factor in the development of the business world. Human resources in the organization are all people involved in developing the company, especially employees. An organization needs a competent and creative employee to achieve organizational goals. Employees have an important role in an organization, namely as thinkers, planners and controllers of organizational activities. Seeing the importance of the role of employees in the organization, employee performance determines the success or achievement of the

company. This study aims to determine whether communication and work environment affect employee performance through motivation as an intervening variable at the Secretariat of the DPRD Labuhanbatu Regency. The study was conducted on 53 employees using a saturated sampling technique. The data collection technique used was primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique used quantitative data which was processed using the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis. The results obtained in this study show 1) there is a significant effect between communication on motivation, 2) there is a significant effect between work environment variables on motivation, 3) there is a significant effect between communication variables on performance, 4) there is a significant effect between work environment variables on performance, 5) there is a significant influence between motivational variables on performance, 6) motivational variables cannot influence communication variables on performance, 7) motivational variables cannot affect work environment variables on performance.

Список літератури:

1. Ernawati, Ambarini. 2010. The Effect of Work Relations and Work Environment on Employee Performance with Work Motivation as a Moderating Variable. *Journal of Economics and Entrepreneurship*. Volume 10. Number 2.
2. Adina Herlista, Handoyo Joko W, and Reni Shinta Dewi. 2013. The Effect of Organizational Culture, Organizational Communication on Employee Performance Through Motivation as an Intervening Variable at Pt. Pln (Persero) Semarang Area.
3. Larasati Dwi Masyitah. 2021. The Effect of Communication and Work Environment on Employee Performance with Motivation as an Intervening Variable. *Journal of Management Science and Research*. Volume 10. Number 11.
4. Audrey Josephine and Dhyah Harjanti. 2017. The Effect of the Work Environment on Employee Performance in the Production Section Through Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable at PT. Trio Corporate Plastic (Tricopla). *AGORA*. Volume 5. Number 3.
5. Agustini, Fauzia. 2011. *Advanced Human Resource Management (First Edition)*. Medan: Madenatera Publisher.
6. Hasibuan, S.P Malayu (2009). *Organization and Basic Motivation to Increase Productivity*. 7th Printing. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.
7. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu. 2013. *Company Human Resource Management (12th Printing)*. Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya.
8. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu (2012). *Company Human Resource Management*. 12th Printing. Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya.
9. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu (2017). *Company Human Resource Management*. 12th Printing. Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya.
10. Sugiyono. 2012. *Business Research Methods*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
11. Sutrisno, Edy. 2011. *Organizational Culture (1st Edition)*. Jakarta: Kencana Publisher (Prenada Media Group).
12. Kuncoro, Mudrajad. 2011. *Research Methods for Business & Economy*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
13. Sugiyono. (2018). *Quantitative Research Methods, Qualitative and R & D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
14. Ghozali, Imam. 2018. *Application of Multivariate Analysis with the IBM SPSS 25 Program*. Jakarta: Diponegoro University Publisher.
15. Husein Umar. 2013. *Research Methods for Thesis and Thesis, Rajawali*, Jakarta.
16. Kuncoro, Mudrajad. 2013. *Research Methods for Business and Economics*. Edition 3. Jakarta: Erlangga
17. Newstrom, John W. & Keith Davis. 2004. *Organizational Behavior 7th Edition*. Jakarta: Erlangga
18. Come on, Gary. 2009. *Leadership in Organizations*. Translated by: Budi Supriyanto. Jakarta: Index
19. Sundari. 2017. The Influence of Communication and Work Environment on Employee Performance at the Regional Development Planning Agency of Sukoharjo Regency With Motivation as an Intervening Variable. *Journal of Accounting and Tax*. Volume 18. Number 1.

References:

1. Ernawati, Ambarini (2010). The Effect of Work Relations and Work Environment on Employee Performance with Work Motivation as a Moderating Variable. *Journal of Economics and Entrepreneurship*, Volume 10, Number 2 [in English].

2. Adina Herlista, Handoyo Joko W, and Reni Shinta Dewi (2013). The Effect of Organizational Culture, Organizational Communication on Employee Performance Through Motivation as an Intervening Variable at Pt. Pln (Persero) Semarang Area [in English].
3. Larasati Dwi Masyitah (2021). The Effect of Communication and Work Environment on Employee Performance with Motivation as an Intervening Variable. Journal of Management Science and Research, Volume 10, Number 11 [in English].
4. Audrey Josephine and Dhyah Harjanti (2017). The Effect of the Work Environment on Employee Performance in the Production Section Through Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable at PT. Trio Corporate Plastic (Tricopla). AGORA, Volume 5, Number 3 [in English].
5. Agustini, Fauzia (2011). Advanced Human Resource Management (First Edition). Medan: Madenatera Publisher [in English].
6. Hasibuan, S.P Malayu (2009). Organization and Basic Motivation to Increase Productivity. 7th Printing. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.
7. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu. 2013. Company Human Resource Management (12th Printing). Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya [in English].
8. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu (2012). Company Human Resource Management. 12th Printing. Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya [in English].
9. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu (2017). Company Human Resource Management. 12th Printing. Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya [in English].
10. Sugiyono (2012). Business Research Methods. Bandung: Alfabeta [in English].
11. Sutrisno, Edy (2011). Organizational Culture (1st Edition). Jakarta: Kencana Publisher (Prenada Media Group) [in English].
12. Kuncoro, Mudrajad (2011). Research Methods for Business & Economy. Jakarta: Erlangga [in English].
13. Sugiyono (2018). Quantitative Research Methods, Qualitative and R & D. Bandung: Alfabeta [in English]
14. Ghozali, Imam (2018). Application of Multivariate Analysis with the IBM SPSS 25 Program. Jakarta: Diponegoro University Publisher [in English].
15. Husein Umar (2013). Research Methods for Thesis and Thesis, Rajawali, Jakarta [in English].
16. Kuncoro, Mudrajad (2013). Research Methods for Business and Economics. Edition 3. Jakarta: Erlangga [in English].
17. Newstrom, John W. & Keith Davis (2004). Organizational Behavior 7th Edition. Jakarta: Erlangga [in English].
18. Come on, Gary (2009). Leadership in Organizations. Translated by: Budi Supriyanto. Jakarta: Index [in English].
19. Sundari (2017). The Influence of Communication and Work Environment on Employee Performance at the Regional Development Planning Agency of Sukoharjo Regency With Motivation as an Intervening Variable. Journal of Accounting and Tax, Volume 18, Number 1 [in English].

Посилання на статтю:

Syafrizal Zan. *The Effect of Communication and Work Environment on Performance With Motivation as an Intervening Variable in the Secretariat DPRD Labuhan Batu* / Syafrizal Zan, Yusuf Ronny Edward, Lenta Friska Purba, Faisal Akbar // *Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал*. – 2023. – № 2 (66). – С. 52-59. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2023/No2/52.pdf>.
DOI: 10.15276/ETR.02.2023.7. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8155029.

Reference a Journal Article:

Syafrizal Zan. *The Effect of Communication and Work Environment on Performance With Motivation as an Intervening Variable in the Secretariat DPRD Labuhan Batu* / Syafrizal Zan, Yusuf Ronny Edward, Lenta Friska Purba, Faisal Akbar // *Economics: time realities. Scientific journal*. – 2023. – № 2 (66). – P. 52-59. – Retrieved from <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2023/No2/52.pdf>.
DOI: 10.15276/ETR.02.2023.7. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8155029.

